

**THE NEW CIVILIZATION OF SPELOTOURISM IN THE
KASHKADARYA REGION**

Ramziddin Khushvaqtov

Student at Karshi State University
xushvaqtovramziddin498@gmail.com

Javohir Turayev

Student at Karshi State University
turayevj423@gmail.com

Annotation:

This article explores the prospects of speleotourism, a newly developing branch of tourism, and its direct impact on the tourism economy. It also extensively discusses the formation of a new civilization of this tourism sector in the Kashkadarya region, as well as the issues and solutions related to the development of speleotourism.

Keywords:

Speleology, Speleotourism, Resources, Cave, Diversification, Infrastructure, Ecotourism, Archaeological, Amir Temur Cave, Chashma Cave, Kizil Cave.

Introduction:

To develop speleotourism, it is essential to consider several factors that influence this sector. It should be noted that speleotourism is currently one of the fastest-growing and important types of tourism. Initially, in Article 36 of the Tourism Law, it is stated under the section on measures to ensure the safety of tourists and excursionists by tour operators and travel agencies that "specific safety requirements must be developed and implemented for organizing and conducting cave tourism and other specialized forms of tourism." Therefore, it is necessary to carry out comprehensive work to further develop speleotourism in our country,

focusing on its future prospects and opportunities.

Literature Review and Methodology

First, we need to understand what this branch of tourism entails. Speleotourism refers to the activity of exploring and utilizing caves and underground systems. This type of tourism primarily involves visiting caves, stalactites, stalagmites, underground water flows, and other natural formations, offering travelers opportunities for adventure and exploration. Speleotourism encompasses ecological, scientific, and cultural aspects since many caves are home to unique ecosystems, and their study plays a crucial role in environmental conservation. Information, guidance, and relevant infrastructure are essential for the safety of visitors involved in cave tourism. Understanding the structure, ecosystems, and formation processes of caves is part of speleology. Speleotourism also includes aspects of environmental protection and groundwater studies. From a scientific perspective, it provides unique sites for adventure seekers, as many researchers engage in active cave tourism.

Additionally, speleotourism, which involves studying caves and underground formations and utilizing them for tourism purposes, began to develop in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Initially, caves were explored solely for scientific and geographical research. However, by the late 1800s, a number of caves were opened to tourists to promote their exploration. Speleotourism on a large scale was first observed in the 1850s in France's "Grotte de la Caverne." Since then, many countries have created opportunities for using caves for tourism. By the mid-20th century, interest in caves and underground formations had become more widespread, leading to the establishment of speleotourism as a recognized sector. Today, this field is closely integrated with ecological tourism, serving purposes of nature conservation and education.

Speleotourism plays an important role in raising ecological awareness and contributing to the local economy. However, focusing on the principles of

sustainability is crucial to protect natural areas and prevent damage to ecosystems. Proper information, guidance, and infrastructure are necessary to ensure the safety of visitors. Cave studies, understanding their structure, ecosystems, and formation processes, are integral to speleotourism. This branch of tourism appeals not only to scientists but also to adventure enthusiasts, as many researchers are actively involved in cave exploration.

Moreover, it can be said that speleotourism has a significant place in the global economy as a form of tourism. In recent years, speleotourism (cave tourism) has had a direct impact on the development of the tourism industry. Let's examine this aspect through a few key factors.

1. **Diversification of Resources:** Speleotourism helps diversify resources by integrating natural attractions, historical landscapes, and sites, contributing to the development of the national economy. Caves and underground systems provide a unique blend of natural beauty and historical significance, attracting tourists and boosting the tourism sector.

2. **Environmental Conservation:** The preservation of caves and their ecosystems is vital for the development of tourism. Strengthening ecological conservation efforts is crucial to maintain the balance between tourism growth and the protection of natural resources, ensuring that the unique habitats within caves are safeguarded.

3. **Preservation of Cultural Heritage:** Caves often hold historical and cultural significance. Through speleotourism, there are enhanced opportunities to study and preserve this heritage. Many caves are linked to ancient civilizations and historical events, making them essential cultural landmarks.

4. **Engagement with Local Communities:** Tourism activities can involve local communities, helping promote their culture and traditions. Local involvement in tourism can lead to increased awareness of indigenous customs and

provide economic benefits to these communities by creating employment opportunities.

5. **Education and Knowledge Sharing:** Educational programs and guided tours offer both local and foreign tourists the chance to learn about ecosystems and geology. Through these initiatives, visitors can gain insights into cave formations, biological diversity, and environmental conservation.

Such factors make speleotourism a unique and important tourism sector. Speleotourism in Uzbekistan holds significant cultural and natural importance. Uzbekistan has many caves and natural formations that enhance its tourism potential. For example, caves around Bukhara and Samarkand may be of interest to tourists, offering not only natural beauty but also opportunities to preserve historical and cultural heritage.

By developing speleotourism, Uzbekistan can also benefit economically, as it will create new jobs and provide a source of income for local communities. To successfully promote speleotourism, it is essential to identify and study all notable caves within the country's regions. Moreover, improving infrastructure, transportation, and services is crucial for supporting tourism development. Environmental protection and adherence to safety standards are also necessary to ensure sustainable tourism practices.

Overall, the development of cave tourism in Uzbekistan presents a key opportunity to combine nature and culture. The adoption of the "Tourism Law" in Uzbekistan is part of the ongoing efforts to create and promote various types of tourism, including speleotourism, which is considered one of the rapidly growing forms of extreme tourism in the country.

For example, Uzbekistan is home to numerous caves and underground natural structures, including those in regions like Chotqol, Qashqadaryo, and Bukhara. Among these, the "Amir Temur Cave" stands out as one of the most significant and well-known to foreign tourists. Located in the Yakkabog district of Qashqadaryo,

the Amir Temur Cave is believed to have great historical value. Local folklore even suggests that Amir Temur's treasures are hidden in the cave.

The Amir Temur Cave is challenging to access, requiring travelers to navigate difficult terrain and natural obstacles. The cave, which is 670 meters long and includes several halls, such as the "Sumalakli Hall" and "Keng Hall," features impressive stalactites and stalagmites. The cave maintains a constant temperature of around 6°C to 7°C, adding to its mystique. Various legends surround the cave, with local residents claiming that its deepest sections hold ancient secrets.

In conclusion, speleotourism in Uzbekistan presents both educational and adventurous opportunities. The preservation of caves like the Amir Temur Cave can provide significant historical and cultural insights while contributing to the growth of Uzbekistan's tourism industry. The development of necessary infrastructure and adherence to environmental protection measures are essential to fully capitalize on this potential.

Beshkent Cave is located in the Beshkent district of the Kashkadarya region, to the northwest of the regional center, the city of Karshi, in a mountainous area surrounded by natural beauty. This cave is an interesting destination for tourists and nature lovers. Beshkent Cave is known for its beautiful nature and historical significance in the Kashkadarya region. The cave is important for archaeological research, as traces of ancient human habitation have been found in it. The interior of Beshkent Cave is adorned with stalactites and stalagmites, which enhances its beauty. There are also fascinating natural landscapes around the cave, making it attractive to tourists and nature lovers. The Beshkent Cave is formed through a karst process, where underground water dissolves rocks. The temperature and humidity inside the cave remain relatively stable, which helps preserve the local flora and fauna. Various mineral stones and crystals are present in the cave, making it interesting for geologists and natural science enthusiasts.

Kizil Cave is located in the Samarkand region of Uzbekistan. This cave is

mainly famous for its karst formations, which include many unique natural shapes and mineral deposits. Various stalactites and stalagmites can also be found inside the cave. Kizil Cave attracts numerous tourists every year. Both local and foreign tourists visit this place to explore it, enjoy its natural beauty, and study its historical significance. The number of visits increases, especially during the summer. Some key features of Kizil Cave include:

Natural formations: The cave contains unique stalactites and stalagmites. These formations were created over many years as water eroded minerals. **Climate:** The temperature inside the cave remains relatively constant throughout the year. It is cool in summer and chilly in winter, providing a comfortable environment for visitors. **Geological significance:** Due to its karst formations, Kizil Cave is a fascinating research area for geologists. **Historical sites:** The cave contains traces and information related to human history.

In the past decade, the number of tourists visiting Kashkadarya for speleotourism has been steadily increasing. In 2013, approximately 5,000 tourists visited annually, but by 2022, this figure had risen to 15,000. This growth has been driven by the natural beauty of the area and improvements in local infrastructure.

According to Otabek Olimjonov, head of the Kashkadarya regional branch of the State Committee for Tourism Development, excursion routes are currently being organized throughout the districts of Mirishkor, Muborak, Yakkabog', Shahrisabz, and Kitob. Additionally, a new tourist route to Amir Temur Cave in the Yakkabog' district is expected to open soon, as reported by Uz24.uz. This place will not only allow foreign tourists and locals to directly visit the cave but also learn detailed information about its history and its connection to our great ancestor, Amir Temur.

Discussion and Results

Based on the analysis of the literature and methodology above, we can conclude that our country possesses sufficient resources to develop the

speleotourism sector to a high level. However, there are certain challenges that negatively affect the growth of this sector. These challenges include:

- Inadequate tourism infrastructure
- Lack of developed opportunities for excursions (in caves)
- Insufficient number of specialists with adequate knowledge and qualifications in this tourism sector
- Insufficient information about these sites in the mass media

Given these challenges, we recognize the need to find solutions. Preliminary research has already identified several potential solutions. Today's modern technologies are capable of addressing almost any problem, but in some tourist regions, there is either no access to these technologies or there is a lack of knowledge on how to use them. However, to solve such issues, one simple path is sufficient. That is, the solution to these problems lies in developing well-rounded individuals with multiple skills. These individuals should possess the following qualities:

- The best guide
- The best information provider
- The highest level of knowledge

So, where do we find individuals with these qualities? The answer is simple: students studying in tourism departments at higher educational institutions. For instance, Karshi State University trains around 100 specialists in this field each year. However, these students are not given comprehensive knowledge and skills specific to the speleotourism sector. Therefore, a speleotourism course should be included in their curriculum for at least one semester. This course should mainly be taught through practical experience. If this is done, students will acquire sufficient knowledge and skills related to cave tourism.

Conclusion and Suggestions

From this article, we can conclude that large-scale efforts are being made to

develop various tourism sectors, including speleotourism. In Kashkadarya region, several practical steps have been taken in this regard, one of which is highlighted in this article. As a suggestion, we propose that sufficient numbers of specialists with the necessary knowledge and skills should be trained for each field. Most importantly, the most convenient way to achieve this without excessive costs is by providing relevant education in higher educational institutions.

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